

**UZBEKISTAN'S SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION WITH ASIAN AND
AFRICAN COUNTRIES IN THE 1960S-1980S.**

Sarvar Akhmedov, PhD student at Karshi State University

***Abstract** This article describes the mutual cooperation of Uzbekistan in the fields of science with the countries of Asia and Africa in the 60s-80s of the 20th century. The transformation of Tashkent into an international center of science, the visit of Asian and African scientists to the scientific institutions of Uzbekistan, and the processes of training of scientific personnel were analyzed in the specific geopolitical conditions of the period. Also, the cooperation of the institutes of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan with foreign scientific centers and its results are shown on the basis of archival documents and historical sources.*

***Keywords:** Uzbekistan, Asia and Africa, scientific cooperation, Tashkent Academy of Sciences, second half of the 20th century.*

Uzbekistan became one of the republics that played an important role in the cooperation of the Soviet state with foreign countries of the Asian region. The international relations of Uzbekistan SSR with the Asian countries in the fields of medicine, agriculture and social and humanitarian sciences have been of special importance.

In Uzbekistan's cooperation with Asian countries, mainly, its relations in the fields of medicine and agriculture have taken a leading place. The city of Tashkent has become one of the places where conferences in the field of medicine of eastern countries are held. In its place, Uzbekistan also conducted preparations for holding such conferences. In 1961, Benaka Belosundara Ray, a microbiologist from the Indian Agricultural Institute, came to Uzbekistan for 2.5 months. During the visit, the scientist studied the activities of the Central Asian Research Institute and the Agricultural Mechanization Station¹.

¹ O'zMA, R-90-fond, 10-ro'yxat, 709-ish, 122-varaq.

The 17th conference of the Pakistan Association for the Development of Science, held in February 1965, was attended by Vice-President of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR Y. Turaqulov, Director of the Institute of Water Problems and Hydrology of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, Doctor of Technical Sciences A.Z. Zohidov, and S.S. Baranov, an employee of the Institute of Asian Peoples of the USSR Academy of Sciences. Y. Turaqulov made reports on the topics “Medical achievements in the study of regional pathology in Uzbekistan” and “Scientific research on the physiology and pathology of the thyroid gland and prospects for the elimination of endemic goiter in Uzbekistan”, while A.Z. Zohidov made a report on the experience of irrigation and development of large areas of land in Central Asia and scientific research related to the use of water resources in Uzbekistan².

In July-August 1961, an international scientific conference on cotton cultivation was held in Tashkent under the auspices of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, and representatives of Pakistan and Afghanistan also participated in it.

In 1970, Professor G. A. Pereverzev, an employee of the Lub Crops Experimental Station, also worked on hemp cultivation in Afghanistan for 1.5 years. The government of Afghanistan awarded 23 Uzbek specialists with orders and medals in accordance with the results of cooperation between the countries in the field of agriculture. In particular, in 1976, scientists and specialists in the field of agriculture of the Uzbek SSR went to Afghanistan to improve the reclamation situation. Specialists of the "Glavzarubejstroy" Department of the Ministry of Irrigation and Reclamation of the Uzbek SSR conducted construction works on the basis of the Jalalabad irrigation system complex in Afghanistan. 4,000 hectares of land have been allocated for the construction of new farms in Afghanistan. Olive trees, citrus trees and grain were grown there⁴.

As part of Uzbekistan's agricultural cooperation with Asian countries, Associate Professor of the Tashkent Agricultural Institute, Director of the Uzbekistan Research

² Корнеев С.Г. Советские ученые - почетные члены иностранных научных учреждений. М.: Наука, 1973; Научные связи АН СССР со странами Азии и Африки. М.: Наука, 1969, С.86.

³ Тухтахўжаев И. Совет Ўзбекистонинг халқаро алоқалари. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 1985. –Б.43.

⁴ Рашидов Р. СССР ва Афғонистон ўртасидаги ҳамкорликнинг ривожланиши. – Тошкент: Фан, 1979. – Б.33-34.

Institute of Plant Protection, C. Alimukhamedov, visited India in 1975 and got acquainted with a new cotton variety created by crossing a local cotton variety. In 1971, scientists from the Sredazgiprovodkhopok Institute participated in the creation of cotton farms on an area of 4 thousand hectares in Syria, and in 1977, they helped acclimatize the "Tashkent-4" cotton variety⁵.

On December 13-14, 1988, a Soviet-Afghan seminar on the topic "Historical roots of friendship and cooperation between the Central Asian republics and Afghanistan" was held at the Abu Raykhan Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. The seminar was organized in cooperation with the Uzbek Society for Friendship and Cultural Relations with Foreign Countries and the Uzbek branch of the Soviet-Afghan Society for Friendship and Cultural Relations and the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR⁶.

During the 60s-80s of the 20th century, Uzbekistan also participated in the international scientific relations of the Union with the countries of the African continent. In particular, although Uzbekistan's cooperation with African countries in the field of exact sciences was not sufficiently established, a certain level of mutual scientific exchanges was carried out. In particular, in 1974, G.Yu. Umarov, a corresponding member of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, visited the African state of Sudan and provided assistance to specialists from this state in the use of solar energy⁷.

Another important area of international cooperation was in the field of medical sciences. It is noteworthy that by this time, international relations in the field of medicine have also been strengthened. The results achieved have been significant not

⁵ Советский Узбекистан сегодня, 1977.– № 7.– С.10.

⁶ Бабаходжаев М.А. Советско-Афганский семинар «Исторические корни дружбы и сотрудничества между советскими Среднеазиатскими республиками и Афганистаном // Общественные науки в Узбекистане, 1989.– №3.– С.60.

⁷ Исаходжаев А.А. Узбекистан страны Арабского Востока Африки. – Тошкент: Узбекистан, 1980.– С.57.

only for the peoples of the region, but also for protecting the health of the world's population.

In September-October 1960, international seminars were held in Tashkent on maternal and child health, and in May 1961 on sanitation, and scientists from African countries also participated in the conferences. In particular, scientists from countries such as Nigeria, Egypt, Ethiopia, Morocco, and Ghana visited⁸. At the same time, in October 1964, Uzbek specialists took part in the Congress of African-Asian doctors in Cairo, the capital of Egypt⁹.

Cooperation in the training of medical personnel has become one of the important directions of Uzbekistan's cooperation with African countries. Since 1962, students from Asian, African, and Latin American countries began to study at the Tashkent Medical Institute. By the 1980s, their number exceeded 170¹⁰.

Within the framework of Uzbekistan's cooperation in the field of science with the countries of the African region, cooperation in the field of medicine was especially important. In particular, during 1970-1976, Uzbek doctor S.Kh.Yakubov worked in Nigeria as part of a technical assistance group of the International Specialized Medical Organizations (ISMO), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the National Tuberculosis Institute. This group carried out work to combat tuberculosis among the population of several states of Nigeria. They carried out treatment of patients, diagnostics and vaccinations, and trained local nurses in the administration of intradermal vaccines¹¹.

From 1975 to 1977, B.A. Tashmatova, an assistant at the Department of Psychiatry at the Tashkent Medical Institute, worked as a specialist at a psychiatric hospital in Addis Ababa, the capital of Ethiopia. B.A. Toshmatova performed electroconvulsive therapy

⁸ Правда Востока, 1964 г. 8 сентябрь.

⁹ O'zFA MA, 1-fond, 4-ro'xat, 314-ish, 52-varaqlar.

¹⁰ Тошкент тиббиёт академиясига 100 йил. Нашрга тайёрловчилар: О.Миртазаев, Т.Бобомуратов. – Тошкент: «O'zbekiston» НМИУ, 2021. – Б.12.

¹¹ Махмудова Н. Во имя мира и дружбы. – Ташкент, 1976. – С.7.

on 1,500 patients and gave a lecture on “Treatment of patients with schizophrenia” at the annual conference of the Ethiopian Medical Association¹².

Thus, during the Soviet period, Uzbekistan's scientific relations with African and Asian countries developed significantly. The main areas of cooperation were the exact sciences, medicine and agriculture. In these areas, fruitful work was carried out with India, Egypt, Algeria and Syria. Geologists of Uzbekistan participated in prospecting and exploration in India, Syria, Iraq and Guinea in the 70s of the 20th century, participating in the discovery of deposits of coal, non-ferrous and rare metal ores, and natural gas.

¹² Исаходжаев А.А. Вклад Узбекской ССР в экономическое, научное и культурное сотрудничество СССР со странами Арабского востока и Африки (1968-1978 годы) дисс...канд.ист.наук: – Ташкент, 1979. – С.85.

